

Notes

Binuclear Alkali and Alkaline Earth Metal Complexes

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THE present study deals with the preparation and characterisation of the complexes of organic acid salts of alkali and alkaline earth metals with 2,4-dinitrosoresorcinol (DNR). DNR acts as a double faced bidentate ligand complexing with alkali and alkaline earth metal salts.

Experimental

A number of complexes having the general formula $[M_aL]_2.DNR$ and $[M_bL_2]_2.DNR$ for alkali and alkaline earth metals, respectively have been obtained, where M_a =alkali metals, M_b =alkaline earth metals, and L=deprotonated organic acids.

The usual method of synthesis was to take DNR in absolute ethanol and added alkali or alkaline earth metal salts (4 : 1) to it. In few cases acetone was used in place of absolute ethanol. These were refluxed for 2-6 h on a steam-bath and then cooled for crystallisation. The adducts were filtered, washed

with absolute ethanol and then dried in air-oven at 80°.

Results and Discussion

All the compounds are stable in dry air, but decompose rapidly on exposure to moisture. The decomposition temperature of the complexes are higher than that of the ligand, showing their greater stability. Some physical properties, as well as analytical results of the complexes are listed in Table 1. The complexes are sparingly soluble in most solvents; but when these are boiled with organic solvents, deposit the alkali and alkaline earth metal salts while DNR goes into solution. The organic acid salts of alkali and alkaline earth metals attached to DNR molecule can easily be decomposed, either by heat or by the action of organic solvents, in which DNR is soluble.

Ir spectra (nujol) for the ligand and complexes were made in the range 4000-650 cm^{-1} . Selected bands in different regions are given in Table 2.

The two strong peaks at 1690 and 1660 cm^{-1} with a shoulder at 1640 cm^{-1} in DNR suggest a quinonoid structure. The peak at 1690 cm^{-1} is too high for a nitroso group and possibly is due to C=O, a dimonoxime. The sharp bands at 3540 and 3420 cm^{-1} in DNR point out that two OH groups are free and not hydrogen bonded.

In the spectra of the complexes, the O-H stretching frequency of DNR is either absent or shifted

TABLE 1

Compd.*	Colour	Decomp. temp. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			
			Metal	N	C	H
(Li-gly) ₂ .DNR	Brown	184	-	16.59 (16.96)	36.38 (36.36)	3.81 (3.63)
(Na-β-alanine) ₂ .DNR	Brown	178	11.81 (11.79)	14.29 (14.35)	42.12 (42.05)	4.44 (4.10)
(K-8HQ) ₂ .DNR	Brown	192	14.80 (14.60)	11.75 (10.48)	54.10 (53.93)	3.21 (2.99)
(K-Anth) ₂ .DNR	Reddish brown	183	15.10 (15.05)	10.83 (10.81)	46.50 (46.33)	3.18 (3.08)
(K-ONBA) ₂ .DNR	Brown	184	13.50 (13.49)	10.35 (9.62)	42.00 (41.52)	2.91 (2.07)
[Mg(8HQ) ₂] ₂ .DNR	Brownish yellow	238	6.00 (6.02)	10.00 (10.60)	63.29 (63.63)	3.47 (3.52)
[Mg(SalH) ₂] ₂ .DNR	Brown	190	7.00 (7.05)	4.06 (4.11)	59.85 (60.00)	3.49 (3.52)
[Ca(SalH) ₂] ₂ .DNR	Brown	185	10.82 (10.92)	3.75 (3.90)	51.00 (51.63)	3.05 (3.27)
[Mg(ONP) ₂] ₂ .DNR	Deep brown	215	6.02 (6.25)	7.09 (7.29)	46.83 (46.87)	2.59 (2.60)
[Ca(ONP) ₂] ₂ .DNR	Deep brown	210	9.91 (10.00)	6.95 (7.00)	45.01 (45.00)	2.43 (2.50)
[Mg(Anth) ₂] ₂ .DNR	Reddish brown	188	6.01 (6.31)	11.00 (11.52)	53.14 (53.43)	3.25 (3.53)

*DNR = Dinitrosoresorcinol, gly = glycine, 8HQ = 8-hydroxyquinoline, Anth = anthranilic acid, ONBA = o-nitrobenzoic acid, SalH = salicylaldehyde.

TABLE 2—SELECTED INFRARED FREQUENCIES (cm⁻¹) OF DNR AND COMPLEXES

Compd.	$\nu_{O...H...O}$	$\nu_{C=O}$	$\nu_{N=O}$
DNR*		1690	1660, 1640 s $\nu_{C=N}$
(Li-gly) ₂ .DNR	2700 br	1620	1590
(Na-β-alanine) ₂ .DNR	2700 br	1660, 1625	1580
(K-8HQ) ₂ .DNR	2650 br	1650, 1620	1590
(K-Anth) ₂ .DNR	2650 br	1660 s, 1620	1590
(K-ONBA) ₂ .DNR		1650, 1620	1575
[(Mg(8HQ) ₂)] ₂ .DNR	2740	1630, 1610	1520
[Mg(SalH) ₂] ₂ .DNR		1630	1520
[Ca(SalH) ₂] ₂ .DNR	2740 br	1600 s	
[Mg(ONP) ₂] ₂ .DNR	2720 br	1600 s	1560
[Ca(ONP) ₂] ₂ .DNR	2720 br	1610	1550
[Mg(Anth) ₂] ₂ .DNR	2720 br	1620	1560

* ν_{O-H} 3540, 3420.

down with reduced intensity, and a new band of medium intensity at ~ 2700 cm⁻¹ is seen in the complexes, which suggest the presence of strong hydrogen bonding. The 1690 cm⁻¹ peak of DNR shifts down to 1660-1600 cm⁻¹ in complexes, which indicate coordination through C=O. The 1660 cm⁻¹ peak with a shoulder at 1640 cm⁻¹ in DNR which is probably due to N=O, is absent in complexes. Instead, one peak is obtained at 1590-1520 cm⁻¹; this may be the C=N peak, which might have coordinated to the metal.

Thermodynamics of Non-Electrolyte Solutions. I. Excess Volumes of Binary Mixtures of 2,2,4-Trimethylpentane with some Alcohols at 40°

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EARLIER¹⁻⁵, excess thermodynamic functions for binary systems containing n-alkane as one of the components have been reported. Benson *et al.*¹ reported excess volumes of C₅- to C₁₆-n-alkanes in n-decanol. Jain *et al.*^{2,3,10} studied excess functions for some n-alkanes in benzene, carbon tetrachloride and silicon tetrachloride. Excess enthalpies of some n-alkanes in cyclohexane have also been reported by some workers⁴⁻⁶. However, the thermodynamic data for isomeric alkanes is only limited^{7,8}. In order to see the effect of branching of alkanes on the magnitude of excess

thermodynamic functions, we have undertaken a systematic study of thermodynamics of isomeric alkanes solutions consisting of solvents of different molecular shape and size. We report here excess volumes of five binary systems of iso-octane (2,2,4-trimethylpentane) with some normal or branched aliphatic alcohols.

Experimental

Chemicals: 2,2,4-Trimethylpentane (L. R. grade) was distilled over sodium metal. Ethanol was purified by distilling a mixture of absolute alcohol and benzene (10:1) where fractions distilling at 64.8° (a ternary azeotrope of benzene, alcohol and water) and at 68.2° (a binary azeotrope of alcohol and benzene) were rejected. Pure alcohol left behind was further distilled over sodium metal.

n-Butanol (L.R. grade), isopropanol (A.R. grade), iso-butanol (for synthesis) and isoamyl alcohol (L.R. grade) were simply distilled before use.

Purity of chemicals was checked by comparing their density and boiling points with the corresponding available literature values⁹.

Method: A bicapillary pycnometer (about 10 ml capacity) was used for measuring the densities of pure components and their mixture at 40°. The details of the apparatus and the method are described elsewhere¹⁰.

Results and Discussion

From the densities of pure components and their mixtures, molar excess volumes have been calculated using the equation

$$v^E = (M_1x_1 + M_2x_2)/d - M_1x_1/d_1 - M_2x_2/d_2 \quad (1)$$

where, v^E is the molar excess volume in ml mol⁻¹, M_i , x_i , and d_i are the molecular weight, the mole fraction and the density of the component i ($i=1, 2$), respectively; d is the density of the mixture.

In Table 1, molar excess volumes of the studied binary systems have been presented. Plots of v^E vs mole fractions of 2,2,4-trimethylpentane have been depicted in Fig. 1. The magnitude of excess volumes at equimolar concentration for the studied alcoholic systems is in the order: isopropanol > ethanol > isobutanol > n-butanol > isoamyl alcohol. It is evident that maximum value of excess volume for each system lies over a composition rich in 2,2,4-trimethylpentane (Fig. 1).